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Ethical checkpoint – a protocol for monitoring participants’ engagement in the AAL4ALL project

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Abstract

AAL technologies for care are an alternative to overloading professionals in the field, as well as promoting active and healthy ageing at home and in the community for as long as possible. However, there are several challenges surrounding their development in terms of ethical and legal suitability, particularly in relation to the security and privacy of end users. In addition, AAL technologies bring up the challenge of clarifying and informing these users who may not have contact with the system's control platforms. In other words, the very passivity of the system makes it difficult for people to understand how it works. This paper aims to demonstrate how the AAL4ALL - From Smart Home to Care (A4A) project approached monitoring users' understanding of how the system works and to report preliminary results obtained through questionnaires and interviews (interim phase) that took place during the implementation phase of the pilot study in Portugal, at Cáritas Coimbra. The pilot study involved installing the A4A solution in the homes of 15 older adults (65+) for 12 months. In Portugal, the AAL4All project is co-

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Introduction

The demographic change due to the ageing of the population, even though predictable, is still surprising in terms of “magnitude and speed”. By 2060, the population aged between 15-64 is expected to decline by nearly 42 million and older people are expected to account for 29,5% of the total population in the European Union (EU, 2014). This kind of projection raises several questions about the way we age and care for ourselves in the digital world.

Ambient Assisted Living technologies show up as a set of technological solutions that help older people in their daily lives, promote their independence and safety, and contribute to enabling people to live autonomously for longer in their own homes. These technologies integrate sensors and intelligent devices capable of being portable and environmental, collecting data in the older adult’s living space to analyse physical and comfort parameters and thus support monitored and personalised care. The assets of these technological developments relate to the quality of life of older people and carers, since AAL environments expect to ease their workload and burden (Calvaresi et al, 2017).

Within this scope, the AAL4ALL- From Smart Home to Care Home (A4A) project aims to enable older persons to stay independent for longer in their own homes by incorporating an ADLAI Platform (for detection of abnormal activities of daily living (ADLs)), room sensor devices (RSD), motion sensors and front door sensors, for data validation and correlation with the RSD data-driven information, and the Anyware Smartphone application for informal and formal care providers. The A4A solution does not include cameras, video or voice recording. The ultimate goal of the project is to democratise the social and healthcare systems by providing those involved with the tools and resources they need to optimise their approach to care.

In the framework of this paper, the idea is to share the approach towards a methodological checkpoint regarding the subjective impressions participants held in terms of clarity about the project mostly related to privacy, safety and data sharing.

Methodological overview

The A4A project encompasses a longitudinal, correlational study, in which the researchers will collect and analyse quantitative and qualitative data from the selected sample of participants during the field trial period (12 months). Due to the observational design of the study, there will be no control group. The pilot phase

will take place in four different countries (Portugal, Romania, Switzerland and Denmark), and the intervention will focus on a participatory and multicentric design, as decisions underlying the field trials process are the results of co-creation and involvement of different partners (business, research and end-users and end-users organisations), and it will be an iterative cycle throughout the project. Beyond that, a lab test and a demo phase were conducted (before the actual field trial implementation) to ensure technological readiness and ethics by design (EC, 2021).

The data collection will be carried out at 70 test homes (70 older adults) in the field trials across the 4 end-user countries. The involvement of the older adults in the trials is in dyads – one older adult plus one caregiver (formal or informal).

To be part of the study the person must be able and willing to provide written consent. The older people able to join the study are (inclusion criteria): the one who demonstrates interest and acceptance of the solution; with an engaged secondary end-user who accepts to be involved; the living alone (or who lives with others but spends most of the day alone); 65+ (however, the participant can be younger if proven need of support is detected, i.e. rehabilitation).

A selection of assessment tools was selected and developed to investigate which are the impacts of the solutions in the piloted social and care settings. Older people should be inquired about their sociodemographic background, quality of life, ADLS deterioration, on the safety, acceptance and functionality of the system (baseline, mid-term and end-line).

The core of this paper reflects on the initiative to include a checkpoint of comprehension and clarity regarding the terms first presented in the Informed Consent as a way to investigate (from a qualitative point of view) their perceptions.

Assessing participants' impressions at the mid-term level

Empirical experience with older adults using passive AAL systems shows some level of difficulty for the primary end-user to comprehend the system and its functionalities (or to retain the information for longer periods). AAL systems as time goes by – and the person does not deal with the control dashboard directly – tend to become a stranger at home. It is even borderline when family members ask for clarifications on what is the system about or why it is there and the primary end-user does not know how to respond anymore.

A4A is a project that included a whole setting of sensors in a person's house, it also included sensors in private areas such as bedrooms and toilets, which complexifies the testing phase. The importance of the information on projects of such nature is even higher, not only in the beginning (for the consent phase) but also throughout the implementation.

It is noteworthy that the informed consent signature already followed a thorough, structured and user-centred protocol to be as friendly, inclusive and clear as possible (CEN, 2023). Beyond that, a very important step of the project was to decide, together with the older adults, which data they would like to share in the system (all participants decided to test the whole system, but they were aware they could turn on/off specific sensors and decide who would have access to the control dashboard – Anyware Software).

The tentative methodological approach the A4A project brought was to include qualitative inquiries in mid-term analysis to perceive how participants were feeling about the solution and if they were still aware of the terms detailed explained and agreed upon during the recruitment phase (for the Informed Consent signature).

Preliminary results

For the purpose of this paper, only the questions developed to address the themes of safety, privacy and data protection will be analysed.

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For the mid-term assessment, 9 evaluation statements/questions (multiple choices and open answers) were included in the interviews regarding participants' feelings and perceptions of the system usage for that timeframe.

The statements/questions and results were (n=14):

1. The A4A solution respects my autonomy and privacy.	57, 1% Totally Agree; 28,6% Agree; 14,3% Neither agree nor disagree
2. I feel safer when I use A4A solution and its equipment.	7,1% Totally Agree; 50% Agree; 35,7% Neither agree nor disagree; 7,1% Totally disagree
3. How safe did A4A make you feel at home?	35,7% higher feeling of safety; 64,3% no changes in the feeling of safety
4. A4A has improved my feeling of safety and peace.	50% Agree; 42,9% Neither agree nor disagree; 7,1% Disagree
5. How often did you remember A4A solution was installed at your home?	7,1% Always; 35,7% Frequently; 14,3% Sometimes; 42,9% Occasionally
6. Are you aware you are the one in charge and who authorizes the data sharing?	100% Yes
7. Explain answer 6. (open answer)	7 people referred they are aware of the data sharing; 2 people referred

	they signed the Informed Consent ; 1 person referred that when the project was presented it was explained; 1 person referred knowing the equipment is installed and that the collected data can be accessed by the researchers; 3 people did not reply.
8. How important do you consider to be in charge of data sharing?	35,7% Very important; 57,1% Important; 7,1% Neutral
9. Which were the most meaningful changes since you joined the project? (open answer)	5 people referred no meaningful changes; 3 people referred they feel safer; 2 people referred they feel they are helping the project; 1 person referred feeling less lonely (due to the contact with the research team); 1 person referred it is an asset for frail people; 1 person referred if the equipment were fully functional he/she would feel safer; 1 person did not reply.

Discussion

The results are only preliminary and are not intended to be an abstract generalization capable of reflecting all tests of AAL sensors for older people. On the contrary, the small sample, selected for convenience, and the qualitative data are intended to reveal the profile of this specific sample and their perception of the system throughout the intervention phase, so that activities could be administered meanwhile to provide clarification and information, if necessary. The methodological approach connects to the good practices for the ethical engagement of participants in digital innovation projects.

According to the results obtained, the participants showed some positive attachment to security and privacy due to the system under test (statements 1, 2, 4), while the majority also reported not often remembering that the system was installed in their home (question 5) - which is precisely what is intended with systems of this type.

However, it is worth noting that in a question of the same nature - about security - the majority of participants answered that they perceived no difference in their feeling of security (question 3). Combined with the final open-ended question (question 9) on the changes felt, the majority of participants reported feeling no difference.

Regarding the selection of data sharing (question 6), it was interesting to see that the entire sample is aware that, although they do not have direct contact with the sensor control application, they are the main ones responsible for deciding how to share the data collected by the system, and can configure and customize it as they wish. The open question was interesting in demonstrating that most of the participants were aware of the information and even remembered where/when they had access to it (informed consent and project presentation).

Conclusion

AAL systems carry with them a paradox that complicates their testing phase in research projects. On one hand, their passive nature should be seen as an asset in terms of comfort and practicality, when it comes to clarifying user understanding this becomes a complicating factor. This is because people end up not interacting with the technology and therefore don't understand its functionalities and associated benefits. Depending on the target group, for example, older people, they may even forget what it's for.

Given this practical challenge, an effort is needed to include active and participatory methods in study protocols to integrate primary users into the testing process in a free and informed manner, while at the same time not promoting discrimination or stigma.

In addition, the testing of sensors in a private environment raises several ethical-legal issues that also need to be addressed in a user-friendly way for the peace of mind and safety of participants, family members and support networks in general.

Therefore, the development of specific materials for the project and its objectives (especially Informed Consent), and a team that is aware of the need to clearly explain the project using appropriate language are essential elements for participation.

In the end, what the paper addresses is the use of the interim phase as an ethical checkpoint to verify that the intended messages have been received by the interlocutors, i.e. that the participants are aware of sensitive issues relevant to a given project so that the research team will still have time and opportunity to act within the intervention phase and the data will serve to qualitatively analyse the system from a person-centred perspective.

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